

An inexpensive system to anneal samples in high-vacuum

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System components:

Description	Distributor	Part number	Price(€)
Hotplate CIMAREC (108 x 108 mm, up to 540°C)	www.ddbiolab.com	078529B	235.00
KF 25 quick-connect to 25.7 mm	www.hositrad.com	KF25/25QDA	61.00
KF 25 hose adaptor (for tubing with 10 mm of ID)	www.hositrad.com	KF25/HN10a	8.00
KF 25 centering ring	www.hositrad.com	KF25/RA	3.00
KF 25 clamp	www.hositrad.com	KF25/C	3.75
100x tubes 25 mm OD 250 mm long	www.labbox.com	TU04-250-100	37.57
2x vacuum tubing 10 mm ID	www.labbox.com	RUTT-010-002	9.48

Home-built part:

A small aluminum part has to be machined in the workshop to transfer the heat from the hotplate to the glass tube. The home-built part is simply a cylinder of aluminum with a flat part (to improve the contact to the hotplate) and with a hole where the glass-tube fits in.

Pumping station:

Our current system uses a dry scroll pump from Tecnovac with an ultimate vacuum limit of 10^{-2} mbar. This pump allows us to perform long vacuum annealing continuously pumping-down and without the need of an exhaust.

Description	Distributor	Part number	Price (€)
Oil-free scroll pump	Tecnovac	ISP-90S50-SV2	2750.00
TPG 361 Strain Gauge	Tecnovac	PT 446 007 -T	995.00

Alternative components for the pumping system:

Description	Distributor	Part number	Price (€)
2-Stage rotary vane pump 4 m3/h	Demaco.nl	3042-00	1990.00
Oil mist filter for pump exhaust	Demaco.nl	RV810220	253.00
301 Busy Bee pirani/capacitance diaphragm gauge	Demaco.nl	PCM301TUTCCA	728.00

A low-cost alternative for the pumping system could employ an air-conditioning rough pump but those pumps cannot be used for long pumping periods.

Description	Distributor	Part number	Price (€)
2-Stage rotary vane pump 120l/min	Amazon	BAOCNEG	189.99
Oil mist filter for pump exhaust	Aliexpress		49.47
301 Busy Bee pirani/capacitance diaphragm gauge	Demaco.nl	PCM301TUTCCA	728.00

Example of use:

In the following figure we illustrate the potential use of this system to anneal devices fabricated with 2D materials. We dry transferred a single layer MoS₂ bridging two pre-patterned gold electrodes separated by ~30 microns (deposited onto a SiO₂/Si chip with 300 nm of SiO₂) and measure its electrical transport characteristics.

Figure caption: The electrical measures of 1L MoS₂ device before and after the annealing process. The output characteristics (a) and transfer characteristics (b) of the 1L MoS₂ device (shown here as an insert in a) before annealing. The output characteristics (c) and transfer characteristics (d) of the 1L MoS₂ device after annealing at 200 degrees in the vacuum for 3 hours.